

Of 502 late maturity local varieties, 7 had very slight, 94 slight, 274 moderate, 126 severe, and 1 very severe infestation.

Of 126 high-yielding improved varieties or cultivars, 4 had very slight infestation (IR9 129-393-3-1-2, IR9 129-169-3-

2-2, IR9224-117-2-3-1 and IR2307-247-2-2-3). The rest had moderate to very severe infestation. ■

Yield loss due to bacterial leaf blight

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Bacterial blight damage was assessed in a field planted with variety Jaya in

Yield differences in bacterial blight-infected rice in Haryana, India.

Infection grade	1	3	5	7	9
Yield loss (%)	6.3	12.3	21	31.6	36.8

Gobindgarh village, Kurukshetra district, during 1981 kharif. The first blight symptoms were observed on 17 August. The disease continued to spread until the first week of September. Plants with different grades of infection by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice

were tagged the last week of August at 4-5 growth stage of the crop. For each disease grade, 100 hills were harvested and yield was compared with yield from 100 healthy hills (see table). Yield loss occurred even at infection grade 1 and increased with grade of infection. ■

Potential sources of blast resistance for hilly regions in India

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Extensive screening for blast resistance in 1978-81 included more than 1,400 local hill rices, about 2,000 improved strains and promising advanced generation bulks from various research centers within India, and about 1,200 cultures from the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP), including the International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN). Natural disease pressure is always extremely high at the experimental farms where screenings were carried out.

High tolerance materials from the preliminary screenings were tested under artificial epiphytotic conditions. Selected materials were also tested at Pithoragarh, Bhowali, Majhera, and Palampur in 1981. All promising entries were tested for neck blast reaction under Almora conditions.

Nineteen entries scored 2 or below (Standard Evaluation System for Rice) at more than 70% of the locations where IRBN has been tested under the IRTP, and conform to the requirements for potential sources of resistance for both leaf and neck blast. IR9292-21-1, VL8, Milyang 46, IR5908-84-2-3-3, IR5931-81-1-1, IR5031-P1p-4B, IR5908-84-2-2, Toride I, and Wagwag combine high blast resistance with medium short maturity and fair cold tolerance. Ta-

poo-choz, Camponi SML, Colombia 11, Dissihatif (73127), IR4547-6-2-5, and RP 1057-35-I-I have medium late maturity and some degree of cold tolerance. Tetep, IR1544-238-2-3, IR3273-339-2-5, and IR1416-128-5-8 also have high tolerance for sheath rot and leaf scald diseases. Except for IR3273-339-2-5, all the listed IR varieties seem to derive their resistance from Tetep.

VL8, Milyang 46, and IR9202-21-1 showed a combination of desirable agronomic features in addition to blast resistance. VL8, a japonica type with some tolerance for *Helminthosporium* disease and some insect pests, is already on the list of released varieties for the hilly regions of Uttar Pradesh. Sufficient quantities of seeds are being produced for immediate use. ■

Evaluation of rice cultivars for resistance to blast and brown spot diseases

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National Screening Nurseries (NSN) 1 and 2 and the International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN) trials during 1981 kharif at Mandya evaluated 954 cultivars for resistance to leaf blast, neck blast, and brown spot diseases. Reactions were recorded under nursery and

transplanted conditions.

Of 386 cultivars screened in NSN 1, 31 showed combined resistance for leaf

blast, neck blast, and brown spot. Only 17 entries in NSN 2 and 17 in the IRBN trial showed combined resistance. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

An improved oviposition cage for rice stem borers

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In the old oviposition cages used to collect stem borer egg masses at IRRI,

many of the egg masses were laid on cage surfaces other than the one designated for oviposition. A new oviposition cage was constructed to force female moths of *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker), *C. polychrysus* (Meyrick), and *Tryporyza incertulas* Walker to oviposit on the desired substrate.

The cage (see figure) consists of a wooden frame 45 cm wide × 52 cm high covered with nylon screen. The cage bottom is wood. Common air conditioner foam rubber filter is stapled on intercage wood surfaces.

The preferred oviposition substrate of wax paper strips (15.24 cm wide × 60.96 cm long) are held in place vertically by slipping the paper through slots in wooden slats at the top and bottom of the cage and securing with tape. Slots are partitioned 12.5 cm apart.

C. suppressalis and *C. polychrysus* pupae in petri dishes were placed in the cage. Female adults that emerged within the cage were observed to oviposit only on the wax paper. *T. incertulas* moths collected around light sources laid 80% of their egg masses on the wax paper.

An improved oviposition cage for rice stem borers, developed at IRRI.

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Varietal reaction to rice gall midge

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Field resistance to rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* was assessed during 1981 kharif on prerelease cultivars and recommended varieties at Aduthurai. Test varieties were grown in 20-m² plots replicated 3 times. Recommended agro-nomic practices were followed except no insect control was used.

Gall midge damage was assessed 60 days after planting as the number of silver shoots among total tillers in 10 hills selected at random from each plot. Rating was by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Of the entries tested only IET3231 had no damage. Five entries recorded less than 5% damage (see table).

Gall midge damage at Tamil Nadu, India, 1981 kharif.

Variety	Parentage	Duration (days)	Damage (%)	Rating
IET3231	IR8/Siam 29	135	0.0	0
IET6010	IR8/W1263	127	0.5	1
IET6290	Leaung/IR8	135	0.8	1
IET6282	Leaung/IR8	130	4.4	3
IET6074	Vijaya/Ptb 21	130	2.3	3
IET5975	OR 10-135/W1263	130	5.0	3
IR20	IR262/TKM6	135	9.1	5
Jaya	TN1/T141	125	9.8	5
Jagannath	Mutant of T141	150	18.0	7
Pankaj (susceptible check)	Peta/Tongai Rotam	150	34.7	7
CD				11.66

Gall midge collections needed

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Discrepancies in reports on host ranges and other biological information on *Orseolia oryzae* in Asia and Africa indi-

cate a need for basic taxonomic research. Such research must be based on adequate collections of reared series from cultivated rice and from suspected wild grass hosts.

The materials needed include adult males and females with associated larvae, pupae, and pupal cases; data on host plant species and cultivars; type of